

Ethical leadership and innovative work behavior among the employees of Jose Rizal Memorial State University Dapitan and Dipolog Campuses

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Abstract

This study aimed to assess the ethical leadership and how it affects the innovative work behavior of the employees at Jose Rizal Memorial State University Dapitan and Dipolog campus during the academic year 2024-2025. It utilized a descriptive correlational research design using the quantitative approach. Three hundred eighty (380) employees participated in the survey. Frequency count, percentage, weighted mean, standard deviation, Kruskal-Wallis H Test, Man Whitney U Test, and Spearman Rank-Order Correlation Coefficient (Spearman rho) were the statistical tools used with Jamovi as the statistical software. The result revealed that fifty percent of the employees of JRMSU were females, they were fairly distributed to the different age brackets, almost 73% pursued graduate and post-graduate studies, 60.27% were 10 years and below in the service, and 51.84% were occupying teaching positions. The level of ethical leadership of employees of JRMSU was very high in terms of ethics of care and ethics of justice but only high in terms of ethics of critique. The level of innovative work behavior of the employees of JRMSU was very high. There existed a significant difference in the level of ethical leadership when the respondents were grouped in terms of gender, age, educational attainment, years of experience, and types of employment. There existed a significant difference in the level of innovative work behavior when the respondents were grouped in terms of age, educational attainment, years of service, and types of employment. However, there was no significant difference in the level of innovative work behavior when the respondents were grouped in terms of gender. There existed a high positive correlation between the levels of ethical leadership and innovative work behavior. Based on the findings, the author recommends that the top officials of JRMSU (Board of Regents and Campus Directors) utilize the findings of this study as valuable input to the University plan for continuous improvement. The employees would use the findings of the study as a source for reflection on their ethical leadership and innovative work behavior.

Keywords: Ethical leadership, innovative work behavior, Jose Rizal Memorial State University

Introduction

Ethical leadership relates to the demonstration of normatively appropriate conduct through personal actions and interpersonal relationships and the promotion of such conduct to colleagues through two ways of communication, reinforcement and decision-making. Ethical leaders foster honest relationships with their employees. Colleagues admire leaders who make ethical decisions, which motivates them to innovate and contribute to organizational success (Ahmed Iqbal *et al.*, 2020) [3]. Ethical leadership focuses on moral dilemmas and associates ethical leadership with employees' moral identification and unethical behaviors (Liu *et al.*, 2023) [14]. An ethical supervisor, as an ethical leader, is expected to influence subordinates' attitudes and behaviors through ethical leadership practices, which encompass prioritizing morality, valuing colleagues,

promoting professional development, enhancing the importance and autonomy of their roles, and making rational and fair decisions.

Innovative work behavior involves intentionally introducing new ideas, processes, products, or procedures within a role, group, or organization, creating something unique or different, and developing usable products, processes, or services by identifying problems and generating new ideas (Al-Omari *et al.*, 2019) [4]. Consequently, employees' innovative work behavior plays an important role to the innovation of an organization. Organizations are under constant pressure to innovate, upgrade, and adapt to keep up with the rapidly evolving technology market. Therefore, an organization's competitiveness is enhanced when its employees are able to innovate and adapt to changing market conditions. Innovation promotes fresh ways of doing

work and helps an organization succeed in this way (Ahmed Iqbal et., 2020) ^[3]. Leaders must now more than ever act morally and ethically because social responsibilities, organization ethics, and morality are becoming more and more important (Yidong & Xinxin, 2013) ^[26].

This study remains underdeveloped despite extensive research on the interconnections between diverse leadership philosophies, creativity, and business transformation (Asif et al., 2023) ^[5]. Numerous supplementary studies have recorded the impact of varied leadership philosophies on improving innovation. Innovative work behavior substantially enhances organizational advancements, growth, and sustainability, yet receives limited scholarly focus. Employees generally demonstrate greater innovative endeavors when ethical managers facilitate innovation implementation, communicate opportunities for employees' personal development, and embrace their failures. The researcher intends to conduct the current study because it has substantial theoretical implications regarding ethical leadership and innovative work behavior within educational institutions, particularly at Jose Rizal Memorial State University, in light of its rapid development.

Objectives

This study aimed to assess the ethical leadership and how it affects innovative work behavior of the employees of Jose Rizal Memorial State University, Dapitan and Dipolog Campuses during the academic year 2024-2025. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 1. Gender;
 2. Age;
 3. Educational Attainment;
 4. Years of Experience; and
 5. Type of Employment?
2. What are the respondents' perceived level of ethical leadership in terms of:
 1. Ethics of Care;
 2. Ethics of Critique; and
 3. Ethics of Justice?
3. What are the respondents' perceived level of innovative work behavior?
4. Is there a significant difference in the respondents' perceived level of ethical leadership when analyzed according to profile?
5. Is there a significant difference in the respondents' perceived level of innovative work behavior when analyzed according to profile?

Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

This study is anchored on Leader-Member Exchange (LMX) theory, leaders and subordinates negotiate their respective roles. This model, in particular, suggests that the relationship between leaders and subordinates' influences innovation. "Under the LMX leadership, group employees tend to have substantial decision-making latitude and thereby could enjoy more time for the negotiated tasks." Outgroup subordinates with less successful role-making processes tend to focus on routine tasks.

Fig 1: Leader Member Exchange Theory

Ethical leadership

Ethical leadership (EL) refers to the display of morally appropriate behavior through personal actions and interpersonal relationships, as well as the encouragement of such behavior among subordinates through two forms of communication: reinforcement and decision making. Ethical leaders uphold exceptionally sincere relationships with their employees (Ahmed Iqbal et al., 2020) ^[3]. Ethical leadership is important for organizations as it enables them to reduce business costs by ensuring fair and moral treatment of employees and other resources. Extensive research has examined the beneficial impact of ethical leadership in reducing the harmful behaviors of employees and discouraging unethical practices in the workplace (Shafique, N Kalyar, & Ahmad, 2018) ^[20].

Ethical leadership can be defined as the demonstration of morally correct behavior through personal actions and interpersonal relationships, as well as the encouragement of such behavior to followers through two-way communication, reinforcement, and decision-making (Khokhar & Zia-ur-Rehman, 2017) ^[12]. Business leaders who adhere to an ethical leadership style are expected to establish a conducive environment that improves the attitude and behavior of their subordinates. Two aspects of ethical leadership are being demonstrated by this definition. Firstly, the moral individual, who adheres to an ethical framework, possesses elevated moral principles such as honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, motivation, and justice. Secondly, the moral leader is an ethical leader who influences the mindset of their subordinates through their leadership conduct (Ullah, Mirza, & Jamil, 2021) ^[26].

Ethical leadership promotes the development of high-quality social exchange relationships, as explained by the social exchange theory. It also influences individuals' perception of a strong connection and unity with the leader, as well as with the unit or organization that the leader represents. This is very probable to incite employees to exert effort and adopt positive attitudes in order to be prepared for any organizational changes (Metwally et al., 2019) ^[17]. Both ethical leadership and an organizational culture of effectiveness prioritize specific aspects that contribute to the overall effectiveness of organizations. For ethical leaders, it is crucial to prioritize the interests of other stakeholders and to go beyond one's own perspective (Kalshoven et al., 2013) ^[9].

Ethics of care

The idea that employees are relational, interdependent entities forms the foundation of the ethic of care. Advocates of the ethic of care, on the other hand, believe that employees are relational and capable of autonomy over the course of their lives (Mathur & Corley, 2014) ^[16]. Ethical leaders do care about their best interests and want to see the employees perform well and reach their potential (Yidong & Xinxin, 2013) ^[26]. When employees feel that their leaders respect them and care about their interests, it makes them believe that they are in a safe climate in the organization (Tu, Lu, Choi, & Guo, 2019) ^[23]. When leaders treat employees with fairness, care, and respect, the employees become more engaged in their work and are more likely to display innovative behavior when confronted with challenging tasks as a result of the appreciation for such treatment. Moreover, when employees experience an increase in psychological safety, it results in higher levels of employee engagement, which in turn allows employees to demonstrate greater innovative work behavior (Liu & Ge, 2020) ^[13].

When employees experience respect and cared from their leaders, they feel compelled to demonstrate positive behavioral reactions in support of their leaders. Furthermore, ethical leaders consistently prioritize the significance of work and integrate purpose into job responsibilities. As a result, employees will perceive a greater sense of purpose in their work and be more inclined to generate innovative ideas that contribute to the organization's advancement towards its goals (Tu & Lu, 2013) ^[22]. When leaders treat employees with fairness, care, and respect, the employees become more engaged in their work and are more inclined to display innovative work behavior when confronted with challenging tasks as a result of their appreciation for such treatment (Liu *et al.*, 2023) ^[14].

Ethics of Critique

Asking why things are the way they are and raising questions is central to the critique ethic. Is school progress impeded by bureaucracy, hierarchy, or complacency; one may wonder? Adopting the critique ethic necessitates being open to considering social justice, as well as issues related to resource distribution, inclusion, and access (Mathur & Corley, 2014) ^[16]. The ethics of critique is a theoretical framework that involves questioning and examining the reasons behind the current state of affairs. Its role is to ensure that employees remain aware of the disparities in social class, race, disability, gender, and other variations that exist within the school community (Lynch, 2018) ^[15].

Ethics of Justice

The decision of an individual to act justly as well as the decision of the school community to act or govern justly are both included in the ethic of justice. The justice ethic offers a framework for problem-solving that starts with determining what is reasonable and equitable for each individual as well as for the school community (Mathur & Corley, 2014) ^[16]. Ethical leader as a moral person characterized by the traits, such as honesty, integrity, altruism, trustworthiness, collective motivation, and justice (Yidong & Xinxin, 2013) ^[26]. Leaders who prioritize justice, trust, and fairness for their followers can enhance the

psychological well-being of individuals and foster a greater sense of meaning in the workplace for employees (Benevene *et al.*, 2018) ^[7]. Employees cultivate a robust sense of accountability and willingly dedicate their efforts to engage in more inventive endeavors for the organization (Khan *et al.*, 2019) ^[11].

Innovative work behavior

Abun *et al.* (2023) ^[1] stated that Innovative work behavior is the behavior that are aimed at the generation, introduction and the application of ideas, processes, products, procedures, new and intended to benefit the relevant unit of adoption. It is widely acknowledged that one of the key tactics used by businesses to stay competitive in the cutthroat economy of today is innovation. The main force behind innovation across the organization is the creative work practices of its employees. The creation of workable goods, procedures, or services through problem-solving and idea generation is considered innovative work behavior (Al-Omari *et al.*, 2019) ^[4]. It is commonly acknowledged that innovation is essential to an organization's success.

Innovation and the ability to innovate at work have become essential for any individual, group, community, organization, or nation to stay up with the times in today's increasingly competitive and demanding global environment (Serdyukov, 2017) ^[19]. Organizations and employees working in extremely competitive marketplaces must act creatively to stay in the organization. An employee's innovative behavior can be described as the steps they take to improve their role performance through the generation, creation, development, application, promotion, realization, and modification of new ideas. (Thurlings *et al.*, 2015) ^[21]. In order for employees to act in a moral and ethical manner while being innovative at work, individuals should provide a clear moral vision to the organization. The ethical values and innovative behaviors of an organization's employees influence its climate.

Based on Statistical Bulletin on Commission on Higher Education (2023) 81,667 (48.82%) of the faculty in the SUCs are males while 85,629 (51.18%) are females. Rocha (2024) ^[18] asserted that most (35.96%) of his respondents were 26-30 years old, (50.88%) of his respondents were college graduates w/ MA/MS Units, and (63.16%) of his respondents were 5 Years & below length of service. Kawasaki (2019) ^[10] study, indicated that about 56.2% of employees belonged to academic positions, and 43.8% belonged to other positions.

Wen *et al.* (2021) ^[25] indicated that the internal mechanism and boundary condition of ethical leadership influencing employees' innovative behavior, which provide a reference for enterprises to encourage employees to innovate, and have important practical significance for employees to actively pursue innovative activities in the workplace. Tu *et al.* (2019) ^[23] stated that when employees feel that their leaders respect them and care about their interests, it makes them believe that they are in a safe climate in the organization. In addition, Liu & Ge (2020) ^[13] stated that when employees experience an increase in psychological safety, it results in higher levels of employee engagement, which in turn allows employees to demonstrate greater innovative work behavior. Liu *et al.* (2023) ^[14] also stated that when leaders treat employees with fairness, care,

and respect, the employees become more engaged in their work and are more inclined to display innovative work behavior when confronted with challenging tasks as a result of their appreciation for such treatment.

Ahmed Iqbal *et al.* (2020) [3] attested that ethical leaders uphold exceptionally sincere relationships with their employees. Shafique *et al.* (2018) [20] examined the beneficial impact of ethical leadership in reducing the harmful behaviors of employees and discouraging unethical practices in the workplace. In addition, the social exchange theory explains that ethical leadership promotes the development of high-quality social exchange relationships. Yuan & Marquardt (2021) [27] claimed that it is commonly acknowledged that innovation is essential to an organization's success. They further stated that within an organization, groups of people as well as individual members can engage in innovative work behavior. It is a more comprehensive term than creativity and includes a range of actions related to the creation, dissemination, and application of novel concepts. Innovative work behavior is the subject of management research, which emphasizes the human side of innovation over its technical side.

Aunin *et al.*, (2024) [6] indicated that gender and type of employment has no significant effect on respondents ethical leadership. They further indicated that age, educational

attainment, and years of experience has significant effect on respondents ethical leadership. Bos-Nehles and Veenendaal (2019) [8], indicated that age, educational attainment, and years of experience have significant effect on respondents innovative work behavior. The finding disagree the study of Bysted (2013), which stated that gender has significant effect on respondents' innovative work behavior.

Employees' ethical leadership and innovative work behavior have an effect on gender and age (Yidong & Xinxin, 2013) [26]. Study revealed that employees' gender, age, educational attainment, and year of experience was significantly differing with ethical leadership and innovative work behavior. Further revealed that ethical leadership is positively related to employees' innovative work behavior. The potential mechanisms between ethical leadership influencing employees' innovative work behaviors (Ahmad *et al.*, 2021) [2].

The conceptual framework is presented in Figure 2. *First*, the demographic profile consists of gender, age, educational attainment, years of experience and types of employment. *Second*, the independent variable which is ethical leadership with three (3) indicators categorized into ethics of care, ethics of critique, and ethics of justice. *Third*, the dependent variable which is innovative work behavior with five items.

Fig 2: Conceptual Framework of the Study

Methods

The study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design using the quantitative approach. The study was conducted in Jose Rizal Memorial State University, Dapitan and Dipolog Campuses, the premier university in the Province of Zamboanga del Norte, Philippines. The respondents of the study were a complete numeration of the three hundred eighty (380) teaching and non-teaching employees including permanent personnel during the

academic year 2024-2025. Data were collected using a survey questionnaire utilizing a five-point Likert scale. The collected data were then tallied, treated, and analyzed using statistical tools such as Standard Deviation, Mann-Whitney U Test, Kruskal-Wallis Test, and Spearman Rank-Order Correlation Coefficient (Spearman Rho), along with descriptive statistics including frequency counts, percentages, and weighted means.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	158	41.58
Female	190	50.00
LGBTQ	32	8.42
Total	380	100.00

Table 1 showed the profile of the respondents in terms of gender. The data claims that exactly half of the respondents are females, 41.58% are males, and 8.42% are LGBTQ. This entails that half of the employees of the Jose Rizal Memorial State University (JRMSU) are females. This result is close to the Commission on Higher Education (2023) data that 81,667 (48.82%) of the faculty in the SUCs are males while 85,629 (51.18%) are females.

Table 2: Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percent
25 & below	37	9.74
26-30	66	17.37
31-35	70	18.42
36-40	44	11.58
41-45	53	13.95
46 & above	110	28.95
Total	380	100.00

Table 2 depicted the profile of the respondents in terms of age. As can be gleaned in the table, more than a quarter (28.95%) of the respondents are 46 years old and above, while age brackets obtained above 9% but less than 19%. This finding indicates that the teaching and non-teaching employees of JRMSU are fairly distributed to the different age brackets. The current finding contradicts with the study of Rocha (2024) [18] which asserted that most (35.96%) of his respondents were 26-30 years old.

Table 3: Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percent
College Graduate	106	27.89
College Graduate w/ MA/MS Units	61	16.05
Master's Degree	81	21.32
Master's Degree w/ Doctoral Units	76	20.00
Doctoral Degree	56	14.74
Total	380	100.00

Table 3 revealed the profile of the respondents in terms of educational attainment. As seen in the table, more than a quarter (27.89%) are college graduates, 21.32% are master's degree holders, one for every five employees are master's degree holders with MA/MS Units, 16.05% are college graduates with MA/MS Units, and 14.74% are doctoral degree holders. This finding signifies that almost 73% of the employees pursued graduate and post-graduate studies. This can be attributed to the fact that promotion in state colleges and universities requires at least a master's degree for the teaching positions. This current finding contradicts with the study of Rocha (2024) [18] which asserted that most (50.88%) of his respondents were College Graduate w/ MA/MS Units.

Table 4: Profile of the respondents in terms of years of experience

Years of Experience	Frequency	Percent
5 years & below	125	32.90
6-10 years	104	27.37
11-15 years	42	11.05
16 years & above	109	28.68
Total	380	100.00

Portrayed in Table 4 is the profile of the respondents in terms of years of experience. The data shows that more than half (60.27%) of the respondents are in the service for 10 years and below and the remaining portion (39.73) are in the service for 11 years and above. This finding implies that the university employed additional new employees to fill in the need for teaching and non-teaching employees in the different campuses and colleges. This finding contradicts with the study of Rocha (2024) [18] which asserted that most (63.16%) of his respondents were 5years & below length of service.

Table 5: Profile of the respondents in terms of types of employment

Types of Employment	Frequency	Percent
Teaching	197	51.84
Non-Teaching	183	48.16
Total	380	100.00

Displayed in Table 5 is the profile of the respondents in terms of the types of employment. The data conveys that the majority (51.84%) of the respondents are in teaching positions while 48.16% are in non-teaching positions. This result can be attributed to the fact that educational institutions need more teachers than non-teaching personnel. The current result backs up Kawasaki (2019) [10] study, which indicated that about 56.2% of employees belonged to academic positions, and 43.8% belonged to other positions.

Perceived level of ethical leadership

Table 6: Summary of the Perceived Level of Ethical Leadership

Ethical Leadership	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
A. Ethics of Care	4.31	0.60	Strongly Agree	Very High
B. Ethics of Critique	4.06	0.63	Agree	High
C. Ethics of Justice	4.31	0.63	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	4.23	0.55	Strongly Agree	Very High

Table 6 summarized the perceived level of ethical leadership. The outcome maintains that the respondents "strongly agree" that the level of ethics of care and ethics of justice is very high while the level of ethics of critique is high. Altogether, the level of ethical leadership is very high. This finding conveys that the ethical leadership of JRMSU is very high. This finding is very significant not only for JRMSU but for every organization. Ahmed Iqbal *et al.* (2020) [3] attested that ethical leaders uphold exceptionally sincere relationships with their employees. Shafique *et al.* (2018) [20] examined the beneficial impact of ethical leadership in reducing the harmful behaviors of employees and discouraging unethical practices in the workplace. In addition, the social exchange theory explains that ethical leadership promotes the development of high-quality social exchange relationships.

Table 7: Perceived Level of Innovative Work Behavior

Innovative Work Behavior (IWB)	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. The employees try to come with creative ideas to improve performance.	4.64	0.61	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. The employees try to find new technologies, processes, techniques, and/or ideas.	4.62	0.64	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. The employees develop adequate plans and schedules for the implementation of new ideas.	4.53	0.67	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. The employees promote and champion ideas to others.	4.47	0.67	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. The employees are innovative persons.	4.58	0.63	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	4.57	0.57	Strongly Agree	Very High

Table 7 illustrated the perceived level of innovative work behavior. The result avers that the respondents “strongly agree” that the employees try to come up with creative ideas to improve performance, find new technologies, processes, techniques, and/or ideas, develop adequate plans and schedules for the implementation of new ideas, promote and champion ideas to others, and are innovative. Overall, the respondents “strongly agree” (mean=4.57, SD=0.57) that the level of innovative work behavior is very high. This finding means that the level of innovative work behavior of the employees of JRMSU is very high. This finding is very important because Yuan & Marquardt (2021) [27] claimed that it is commonly acknowledged that innovation is essential to an organization's success. They further stated that within an organization, groups of people as well as individual members can engage in innovative work behavior. It is a more comprehensive term than creativity and includes a range of actions related to the creation, dissemination, and application of novel concepts. Innovative work behavior is the subject of management research, which emphasizes the human side of innovation over its technical side.

Difference in the Perceived Level of Ethical Leadership

Table 8: Test of Difference in the Perceived Level of Ethical Leadership when the Respondents are grouped in Terms of their Profile

Profile	H Value	U-Value	p-value	Interpretation
Gender	1.264		0.004	Significant
Age	24.201		< 0.01	Significant
Educational Attainment	46.717		< 0.01	Significant
Years of Experience	18.720		< 0.01	Significant
Type of Employment		14015.500	< 0.01	Significant

Table 8 presented the test of difference in the perceived level of ethical leadership when the respondents are grouped in terms of their profile. Using the Kruskal-Wallis H test and Mann-Whitney U Test, the result revealed that there exists a significant difference in the perceived level of ethical leadership when the respondents are grouped according to their profile. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This finding implies that the respondents' perception of ethical leadership is significantly affected by their gender, age, educational attainment, years of service, and types of employment. This finding further implies that male and female, young and old, bachelor's degree, master's degree, and doctoral degree holders, experienced and non-experienced employees, and teaching and non-teaching

employees have different perceptions of ethical leadership. Aunin *et al.*, (2024) [6] study indicated that gender and type of employment has no significant effect on respondents' ethical leadership. However, they indicated that age, educational attainment, and years of experience have significant effect on respondents' ethical leadership.

Difference in the Perceived Level of Innovative Work Behavior

Table 9: Test of Difference in the Perceived Level of Innovative Work Behavior when the Respondents are grouped in Terms of their Profile

Profile	H Value	U-Value	p-value	Interpretation
Gender	2.837		0.242	Not Significant
Age	31.672		< 0.01	Significant
Educational Attainment	47.204		< 0.01	Significant
Years of Experience	29.297		< 0.01	Significant
Type of Employment		13252.500	< 0.01	Significant

Table 9 portrayed the test of difference in the perceived level of innovative work behavior when the respondents are grouped in terms of their profile. Applying the Kruskal-Wallis H test, the outcome asserts that there exists a significant difference in the perceived level of innovative work behavior when the respondents are grouped in terms of age, educational attainment, years of experience, and type of employment. Thus, the hypotheses for these variables are rejected. This finding entails that the respondents' age, educational attainment, years of experience, and type of employment significantly affected their perception of innovative work behavior. However, there is no significant difference in the perceived level of innovative work behavior when the respondents are grouped in terms of their gender. Thus, the null hypothesis for this variable is not rejected. This finding denotes that male, female, and LGBTQ employees have the same perception of innovative work behavior. This finding further denotes that the respondents' perception of innovative work behavior is not significantly affected by their gender. This finding is supported by Bos-Nehles and Veenendaal (2019) [8] who indicated that age, educational attainment, and years of experience have significant effect on respondents' innovative work behavior. However, this finding disagrees with the study of Bysted (2013), which stated that gender has significant effect on respondents' innovative work behavior.

Relationship between Ethical Leadership and Innovative Work Behavior

Table 10: Test of Relationship between Ethical Leadership and Innovative Work Behavior

Ethical Leadership	rho-value p-value	Innovative Work Behavior	Interpretation
Ethics of Care	rho-value p-value	0.570 < 0.01	Large/High Positive Correlation Significant
Ethics of Critique	rho-value p-value	0.523 < 0.01	Large/High Positive Correlation Significant
Ethics of Justice	rho-value p-value	0.566 < 0.01	Large/High Positive Correlation Significant
Overall	rho-value p-value	0.634 < 0.01	Large/High Positive Correlation Significant

Table 10 disclosed the test of relationship between the ethical leadership and innovative work behavior. When the dataset is subjected to the Spearman Rank-Order Correlation Coefficient (Spearman rho), it yielded p-values less than 0.01 which indicates that there exists a significant relationship between the levels of ethical leadership and innovative work behavior. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This finding indicates that as the level of ethical leadership increases, the level of innovative work behavior also increases. This finding further indicates that the level of innovative work behavior is significantly affected by the level of ethical leadership. This finding furthermore indicates that ethical leadership and innovative work behavior are highly and positively correlated. This finding is consistent with the study of Asif *et al.*, (2023) [5], which indicated that ethical leadership has a significant relationship with employees' innovative work behavior. They further indicated that strong ethical convictions and consistent ethical normative behavior among leaders can influence employees' drive, i.e., willingness to work hard, which inevitably will be reflected in indications of innovative workplace behavior.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the study concluded that Fifty percent (50%) of the employees of JRMSU were females, they were fairly distributed to the different age brackets, almost 73% pursued graduate and post-graduate studies, 60.27% were 10 years and below in the service, and 51.84% were occupying teaching positions. The level of ethical leadership of employees of JRMSU was very high in terms of ethics of care and ethics of justice but only high in terms of ethics of critique. Meanwhile, the level of innovative work behavior of the employees of JRMSU was very high. A significant difference in the level of ethical leadership was observed when the respondents were grouped in terms of gender, age, educational attainment, years of service, and types of employment and a significant difference in the level of innovative work behavior was noted when the respondents were grouped in terms of age, educational attainment, years of service, and type of employment. However, no significant difference was seen in the level of innovative work behavior when the respondents were grouped in terms of gender. Moreover, there is a high positive correlation between the levels of ethical leadership and innovative work behavior was discovered. Thus, the top officials of JRMSU (Board of Regents) may utilize the findings of this study as valuable input to the University

plan for continuous improvement. The campus directors on the other hand, may also utilize the findings of this study as bases for the enhancement of ethical leadership and innovative work behavior of the employees. Lastly, employees may also use the findings of the study as a source for reflection on their ethical leadership and innovative work behavior.

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